

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 18, No. 20

Dear Readers,

In the last issues of volume 18, I'd like to take the opportunity to thank all members of the J.UCS consortium for their financial and organizational support which makes it possible to keep J.UCS an open access journal for readers and publication fees-free journal for authors. I'd also like to thank the authors for their contribution and all members of the editorial board for their thorough reviews which are essential to guarantee the high quality of the journal.

In a retrospective view of the 18th volume, we have published 45 papers in six regular issues and another 91 papers in 14 special issues. With a total of 136 accepted and 414 rejected papers, we can report an acceptance rate of 24.7 percent. In 2012, we had some 22,225 hits and 1,375 full text downloads of PDFs per day on average. On the technical and organizational side, we have improved the measures of user statistics and the more widespread connection with social media.

For 2013, I am looking forward to working together with our editors, the editorial team and the technical support to continue the success of J.UCS. I would also be very grateful for suggestions and feedback on how we could even further improve and develop J.UCS in the next years. We are already working on a new paper submission and review system to further streamline and speed up the review process. We also want to further increase the number of consortium member to guarantee the sustainability and the openness of the journal.

In this last issue of this year we also have a contribution to the 'Forum for Negative Results' initiated and administered by the guest editor and editorial board member Prof. Lutz Prechelt (see also the guest editorial in this issue) as well as 7 other papers, all of which have passed the J.UCS evaluation process. Following our strategy to be open for all topics in computer science, in this issue we have a broad spectrum of very interesting subjects from computational analysis to security aspects in distributed systems. Enjoy reading the eight papers!

Cordially,

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